

Quintessential of Hybrid Legal Library: A Case Analysis of Miyetti Law Library

Wisdom O. Anyim¹

Miyetti Law Library, Abuja, Nigeria

Email: wisdomaris@gmail.com

Margaret N. Ngwuchukwu

Department of Library and Information Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Email: margaret.ngwuchukwu@unn.edu.ng

Abstract: The paper attempts to discuss the fast development of Information Technology and its application in the legal library services with the Miyetti Law library as a case study. Miyetti law library is a typical example of a hybrid legal library equipped with necessary resources in order to accomplish the newly Information Technology based services. Hybrid legal libraries with adequate Information Technology-enabled services facilitate the fulfillment of the information needs of the users at the right time without the barrier of distance and space. The paper discusses emerging technologies, services, and retrieval tools that make hybrid library worth implemented.

Keywords: Hybrid, Hybrid library, Law library, Information Technology, Electronic Library, Miyetti Law, Miyetti Law library

Introduction:

Information is an essential commodity for human development. Lawyers depend on accurate information to be able to dispense justice. This makes the law library a thriving hub for lawyers, legal researchers, paralegals, and students of Law. The wave of change triggered by new information technologies has a tremendous effect on the way information is stored, accessed, retrieved, and disseminated. This also affects the information-seeking behavior of users. The increasing breakthrough in information technology in library services makes it difficult for libraries to dwell on the conventional method of service delivery. The traditional method of library operation alone no longer weighs balance in the 21st-century requirements. The only way library can fulfill its mandate is to integrate both traditional and electronic-based resources and services in a singular system referred to as “hybrid library”.

Hybrid libraries are blends of traditional print material such as books and books as well as electronic-based material such as downloadable electronic books, electronic journals, e-books, audiobooks, and other web resources. Hybrid libraries are a 21st-century trend in legal information services. It evolved as the product of the Information Technology revolution in libraries making electronic resources to gain wider acceptance into libraries. Electronic resources were mainly material distributed on media such as CD-ROM or searches of specialized databases before OCLC assisted in pushing libraries towards acquiring digital resources through a centralized technology resource for participating libraries (Michael, 2002). As a result of the widespread availability of digital content, hybrid libraries include web resources and documents which are searchable online.

¹ Corresponding author

Trends in Legal Libraries:

Most law libraries all over the world now operate the so-called ‘Hybrid Library’ - a combination of print materials and electronic materials. For any law library to thrive in the 21st Century, it is not a matter of choice to have a hybrid library, but the right thing to do. The technological changes that ushered the world into the so-called Information Society have at the same time made libraries make a paradigm change from analog to the digital environment.

The convergence of computer technology and communication technology that gave the right to the Internet in 1969 and the World Wide Web in 1993/94 changed the world and affected all public domain activities – law, education, governance, medicine, social interaction, communication, commerce, etc. Now terms such as e-lawyering, e-learning, e-commerce, e-government, e-medicine, etc. have emerged to describe new ways of doing things using computer and information technology.

Librarianship being a very important public domain institution developed its own electronic variant called e-library. Legal libraries, a subunit in the legal ecosystem, under intense pressure by the legal society have developed a hybrid library made up of analog materials² and electronic library. With the effect of globalization, libraries all over the world are following the same pattern. In Nigeria, the admissibility of computer-generated evidence by law has given a boost to the development of hybrid legal libraries. Recently, the legal library environment has continued to undergo changes induced by Information and Communication Technology. The observable changes include;

- i. Most of the library operations have been fully automated using an Integrated Library Management System which provides modules for cataloging, catalog (Online Public Access Catalogue), patron management, circulation, fines management, acquisition, use of barcodes, and bar code reader, management reports, and many other tools.
- ii. Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) has replaced the catalog card cabinet and the 5X3 catalog cards. OPAC is one of the features that make up the library’s Homepage on the Internet.
- iii. Library materials are tagged with electronic tags for easy stock taking, retrieval from the shelf, and checkout.

The Traditional Law Library Environment:

Before ICT invaded the library, the law library was made up of the library building strategically located in the court, law firm, law colleges, legal institutes and legal units of various organizations, etc. Then, legal books and non-book materials were well-arranged into subject areas of law with trained legal librarians manned the administration of the library. Reading space also makes up the component of the traditional legal library.

The Electronic Law Library Environment:

² print materials

Electronic libraries, digital libraries, and virtual libraries mean the same type of library. They refer to a library with the following features;

- i. The information materials are in digital formats.
- ii. The materials are well structured for easy retrieval of information.
- iii. Network-based.
- iv. The library is accessible 24 hours a day and 7 days a week.
- v. Well librarians with the skills to manage the application software in place and structure the digital resources.

Unlike the traditional library, the electronic component is not stationary based. It is a part of the Internet and therefore can be hosted anywhere in the world and accessible through the Internet. The so-called electronic library is not one application system, rather it is a suite of application systems deployed online and made available to users through a well-designed online interface.

Hybrid law library online interface has about six components:

- i. Online Public Access Catalogue
- ii. Electronic books powered by the electronic library application system
- iii. Online Journals powered by Electronic Resource Management System
- iv. Collection of owned intellectual output powered by an Institutional Repository System
- v. A federated search engine capable of searching across the above-mentioned systems.
- vi. Web links to important websites of interest to the library users.
- vii. General information area – news, library staff, and library rules, etc.

Legal libraries have changed to be 21st Century ICT compliant in order to meet up with the demands of ‘net citizens’ - the new generation lawyers who grew up depending on the Internet and mobile network for their needs. Some writers refer to them as ‘born digitals. For born digitals anything that is not on the Internet does not exist, including library materials.

Overview of Miyetti Law Library:

Miyetti Law is a boutique law firm strategically located at the federal capital territory, Abuja, Nigeria with legal luminaries and experts who pursue the objective of the firm to remain the clients’ favorite legal hub. Miyetti Law has a legal team with over two decades of practice experience and advanced degrees, and have represented clients in Supreme, Court of appeal, and High Courts, worked in human rights organizations, founded non-governmental organizations, engaged in several Pro bono services, worked for national and multi-national organizations and companies, taught at Law Schools in Nigeria and Abroad. Miyetti Law engages in transactional work, business planning, interfacing with government entities, and individual clients. Advocacy and legal advice to clients around the globe are part of the services rendered by the firm. Miyetti Law supplies well-rounded assistance by providing a platform where individuals, businesses, charity organizations, and government agencies can better achieve their goals (Miyetti law library, *n. d.*)

Miyetti Law Library adopts best practices that meet its firm’s objectives by integrating all genres of traditional and electronic resources and equipment that meet diverse research needs. Ever since the Library was established in 2015, several steps have been taken in surveying the Lawyers’ information needs within and outside Nigeria which were very necessary in determining what resources and equipment would be required in order to emerge a leader and “one-stop-shop” for legal information services in Nigeria. The Library, first and foremost, recognized the importance of creating formidable legal resources with up-to-date contents and retrieval tools necessary for accessing and retrieving information. These are the first requirements that the library put into consideration to ensure that resources available are current, overlapping, and representative of diverse areas of Law (Miyetti law library, *n. d.*).

Miyetti Law Library resources represent a stock of hybrid legal materials that include Nigerian Law Reports, British Law Reports, Law Reports of the Commonwealth, other foreign and English Law Reports; Practitioners’ Textbooks in diverse areas of Law; Law Peer Reviewed Journals; Statutory instruments; law digest, Atkins court form, other case laws from a different jurisdiction, International and Local Agencies’ Publications.

The hybrid standard of Miyetti Law library attracts high patronage from users across the country. Meanwhile, the central focus of the library is to employ available technologies and traditional mechanisms capable of solving information puzzles within the ambit of the legal profession. The library employed the latest Mac desktops and laptops connected to 24 hours internet. Databases of both foreign and local jurisdictions were made available to enable users to gain access to any form of legal documents. The subscribed databases include:

- i. Westlaw UK,
- ii. Practical Law,
- iii. Heinonline,
- iv. Lexis-Nexis,
- v. Legalpedia,
- vi. Law Pavilion;
- vii. e-portals
- viii. and open sources.

WIFI is also made available to users for a free internet connection to their PCs. Miyetti Law Library is manned by a team of trained and experienced librarians and technical experts with track records. As crucial in the legal information industry, the librarians of Miyetti Law Library undergo continuous training and workshop within and outside Nigeria. The librarians also attend the International Bar Association (IBA) Conferences to enable them to get abreast of innovations in legal information management.

As many hybrid libraries across the globe engage in content creation and production, Miyetti Law publishes a law journal with articles focused on the specific areas of law such as immigration, energy policy, international legal developments, corporate law, etc. The firm follows the important developments in all fields clients are interested in and provides a factual analysis of new developments that shape and affect the adjudication of justice (Miyetti Law, *n. d.*).

Table 1: Medium of Activities in Miyetti Law Library

S No	Activities	Traditional Medium	Electronic Medium
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1	Generate	Writing, Typing	Word processing, text editing, character recognition, voice recognition
2	Acquisition	Purchase, donation, gift	Subscription
3	Storage	Manuscript, Paper-print media	Electronic publishing, magnetic storage, computer disc, cloud storage
4	Retrieval	Print indexes, abstracts, bibliographies, catalogues	Electronic data processing
5	Dissemination	Hard copies	E-mail, website, video-conferencing, SMS, SDI, CAS
6	Preservation	Filing	Digital archiving
7	Security	Mobile human security	Surveillance, Digital camera, RFID
8	Users' Registration	In-person	Online

Information Retrieval in Hybrid Legal Libraries System:

It is normal in the legal community to find lawyers who lack knowledge of the use of either traditional information retrieval tools or electronic retrieval tools. Most of the lawyers especially, the old ones are conversant with traditional retrieval medium than electronic. They have the ability to access information resources through the catalog, shelve guides, or simply navigate through indexes while conducting library research. Without retrieval tools, lawyers can walk through an avalanche of information in the library or database only to find it difficult to locate relevant and accurate information they need. Locating any kind of information in the databases or library domain requires effective knowledge and the use of information retrieval tools.

With the proliferation of information on legal information resources, accessibility, and retrieval of information can only be achieved using retrieval tools. Opijnen and Santos (2017) opine that the emergence of information technology and the open data movement gives an astronomical rise in the number of legal documents published online which require corresponding accessibility and searchability. Information retrieval is referred to a process that enables us to organize, locate, and retrieve encoded information in an information system or in print. Chimah, Unagha, and Nwokocha (2010) describe information retrieval as a process that involves the retrieval of information from a collection or database in response to an information problem. Information retrieval involves the act of searching and retrieving needed information from a database or traditional retrieval tools.

In hybrid libraries, information retrieval involves certain approaches that utilize reference tools such as catalog, index, search engines, and other applications to access relevant information from books or databases. The effectiveness of a library is determined by its ability to provide the users with the necessary tools capable of accessing and retrieving information. With information retrieval tools, information seekers are enabled to quickly and efficiently search, find/or locate and retrieve their needed information resources (Echem and Udo-anyanwu, 2018).

To facilitate the process of selecting information from storage devices or carriers is what information retrieval does in a hybrid library. However, the process is dependent on physical mechanisms in library collections and or computers/technologies information system designs. The legal information environment of the digital age requires basic knowledge and understanding of retrieval tools to facilitate access to information. Equipping users with knowledge about access tools available to them in order to assist them to explore opportunities provided in a new information environment is crucial in the 21st century (Afebende and Nna-Etuk, 2019).

Hybrids libraries combine mechanize and traditional retrieval tools to give users access to any kind of information they need. Information retrieval tools are systems designed to guarantee ease of access or retrieval of information in an organized information record or database directing users to particular types of information sources. Some of the traditional tools in libraries include catalogs, Indexes, abstracts, and bibliographies. In recent times due to developments in ICTs, computerized access tools have begun to offer full-text access to digital documents in addition to bibliographic records (Afebende and Nna-Etuk, 2019; Nwosu and Ottong (2014) & Ojedokun (2007).

Discovery through literature is a number of information retrieval tools that lawyers around the world utilize most often; these include catalogs, Indexes, abstracts and bibliographies, internet search engines, shelf-guide, web-based information retrieval system, (Ademodi and Akintowide, 2012; Ojedokun, 2007; Nnadozie, 2007 & Okafor, 2006).

The conventional system of retrieving particular information is no longer enough in the present time where legal libraries have adopted a hybrid library system. Lawyers can now search through web-based indexes, abstracts, and databases, Online Public Access Catalogue, and bibliographies to obtain information from the body of knowledge. Libraries provide users with retrieval tools to access relevant articles in magazines and journal case laws, legislations, and other statutory information (Rowley and Farrow, 2000).

However, to limit the role of legal information retrieval within the daily legal practice to just finding the court decisions relevant to the case at hand underestimates the complexities of the law and of legal information-seeking behavior. Any legal information retrieval system built without sufficient knowledge, not just of the actual legal information needs but also of the ‘juristic mind’, is apt to fail” (Opijnen and Santos, 2017).

Table 2: Retrieval Tools in Miyetti Law Library

Information Retrieval Tools
OPAC
Search Engines
Indexes
Abstracts
Bibliographies
Shelve guide

Miyetti Law Library has a combination of traditional and electronic retrieval tools that facilitate research. Its Online Public Access Catalogue enables researchers to see the holdings of the library and location where such resources could be found on the shelves and digital archives. For registered users who are not physically present in the library, they can through the OPAC access what resources are available in the library and utilize their borrowing privilege.³

There is a research guide that equips the users on how to utilize search engines, indexes, abstracts, bibliographies, shelves guides, and other assisted retrieval tools. In addition, lawyers are also trained in the use of information retrieval tools available in the library.

Technologies and Tools Supporting Hybrid Legal Libraries:

³ this is mostly allowed for in-house legal staff.

Basic technologies in hybrid legal libraries are discussed under the following headings:

- i. **Computers:** Computer-based technologies have become transformational tools for shaping and reshaping the products and services the legal library offers. The success of the IT-enabled services in the library is based on the efficiency of the equipment provided in the library i.e. most modern technology, not on the basis of the number of equipment (Vijayakumar and Vijayan, 2011). Miyetti Law Library has first-class computer-based technologies, the latest that could be found in the industry of the 21st century. Not only that the library deploys latest Mac computers but also installs effective server and strong internet network that facilitate IT-enabled services in the library.
- ii. **OPAC:** An Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) is an online database of materials held by a library or group of libraries. Users search a library catalog for the purpose of locating books and other material physically present at a library (Online Encyclopedia, *n. d.*). This is also provided by the Miyetti law library to enable the lawyers and legal researchers to locate the resources available in the library. Materials in the library are classified using the Moys classification scheme.
- iii. **CD-ROM:** This type of technology is very crucial in a hybrid library. It contains information, such that could have been found in books and other sources of information. At Miyetti law library, CD-ROM containing vital information such as case laws, legislation, rules, and so on are made available for users.
- iv. **Scanner:** “In computing, an image scanner—often abbreviated to the just scanner— is a device that optically scans images, printed text, handwriting, or an object, and converts it to a digital image. Mechanically driven scanners that move the document are typically used for large-format documents, where a flatbed design would be impractical” (Online Encyclopedia, *n. d.*). Miyetti law library provides users with a 3D scanner that gives users a feel of modernity.
- v. **RFID:** Radiofrequency identification simply refers to technologies utilizing radio waves for identifying individual items automatically. The most common way is storing a serial number identifying a book and related information on a microchip attached to an antenna. RFID is used very similar to bar codes (Mehrjerdi, 2011). This very technology is still an ongoing project in the Miyetti Law Library.
- vi. **Facsimile:** A facsimile is a technology that makes a copy or reproduction of an old book, manuscript, map, art, or other items of historical value that is as true to the original source as possible. It differs from other forms of reproduction by attempting to replicate the source as accurately as possible in terms of scale, color, condition, and other material qualities. For books and manuscripts, this also entails a complete copy of all pages; hence an incomplete copy is a “partial facsimile” (Online Encyclopedia, *n. d.*).
- vii. **Photocopy:** A photocopier is a machine that produces paper copies of documents and other visual images as quickly and cheaply as possible. Most current photocopiers use a technology called xerography, a dry process using heat. Photocopying is widely used in the library. Miyetti law library operates a cloud-based photocopier that produces copies of documents as pure as the original documents.

- viii. **Printing technology:** In computing, a printer is a peripheral which produces a text and/or graphics of documents stored in electronic form, usually on physical print media such as paper or transparencies. Miyetti law library operates a 3D printing technology that makes printed works look real and brilliant.
- ix. **Barcode:** A barcode reader or barcode scanner is an electronic device used for reading printed barcodes. Like a flatbed scanner, it consists of a light source, a lens and a light sensor converting optical impulses into electrical ones. Most barcode readers contain decoder circuitry analyzing the barcode's image data provided by the sensor and sending the barcode's content to the scanner's output port (Online Encyclopedia, *n. d.*).
- x. **Audiovisual materials:** The Audiovisual collection contains a wide range of audio-visual material to support the research and study needs of staff and students (University of Canterbury, *n. d.*).
- xi. **Internet:** Information Technologies revolutionize communication and make information dissemination easier and faster which enhances decision making. The internet which is the latest among the superhighways has cut down the distance and made access to information easier for all people without barriers to distance and space (Kaul, 2004). Internet provision in the Miyetti law library is "one-touch, instant result."
- xii. **Library website:** Library website helps to recognize the facilities and information sources available in the library. In most of the library website, the online catalog is included. The online catalog helps to ascertain a client whether the information is available in the library (Vijayakumar and Vijayan, 2011). Miyetti law library has a functional library webpage featured on the Miyetti law website. From this website, information or news related to the resources and services of the library is made open for the general public.
- xiii. **Database:** A database is an organized collection of data for one or more purposes, usually in digital form. The data are typically organized to model relevant aspects of reality, in a way that supports processes requiring the information (Ullman and Widom, 1997). Miyetti law library subscribes to a number of local and international databases which include: Westlaw, Lexis-Nexis, Practical Law, Heinonline, Law Pavillion, Legalpaedia, All Weekly Law Report Online.

Technologies Supporting User Services in Hybrid Legal Libraries:

- i. **Document delivery services:** The Document Delivery Service (DDS) delivers copies of journal articles and book chapters from participating Libraries. Fees apply for most Document Delivery Services. To fulfill the information needs of the end-user through information/document supply is a document delivery service. This service is provided on a No Profit - No Loss Basis and Expected to be prompt (UC Davis Library, *n. d.*). Miyetti law library engages in document delivery services only to the registered members through e-mails only.
- ii. **Interlibrary loan:** an interlibrary loan involves collaboration among libraries by which one library may borrow material from another library. In other words a loan of library materials by one library to another library (Vijayakumar and Vijayan, 2011).

- iii. **Indexing and abstracting services:** These services are very important in a hybrid legal library but not compulsory as these depend on the objective, human resources capacity and expertise of the workforce that make up the law library (Kawatara, 2002). Miyetti law library does not engage in these services.
- iv. **Chat services:** Online chat includes any kind of communication over the Internet, that offers instantaneous transmission of-text-based messages from sender to receiver, hence the delay for visual access to the sent message shall not hamper the flow of communications in any of the directions. Online chat may address as well as point-to-point communications as well as multicast communications from one sender to many receivers (Online Encyclopedia, *n. d.*). Chat service is available at Miyetti law library and is handled by the executive secretary's department of the firm.
- v. **CAS:** The aim of a current-awareness service is to inform the users about new acquisitions in their libraries. Public libraries in particular have used display boards and shelves to draw attention to recent additions, and many libraries produce complete or selective lists for circulation to patrons. Some libraries have adopted a practice of selective dissemination of information (Britannica, *n. d.*). Miyetti law library uses computer-based technology to notify the registered members of the new arrival of materials in the library. They go to an extent of forwarding the bibliographic details and table of contents of the items to the users through email or telecommunication.
- vi. **SDI:** Selective dissemination of information (SDI) is a common phrase in the field of library and information science. It refers to the tools and resources used to keep a user informed of new resources on specified topics. Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) was a concept first described by Hans Peter Luhn of IBM in the 1950s (Britannica, *n. d.*). At Miyetti law library, librarians are conversant with research areas of the users and regularly update them on any new information, laws, cases; articles, etc. that will enhance their research objectives.
- vii. **Scanned copies:** A scanning service for material not available electronically, which is held by the Library. This includes articles from journals and chapters from books (University of Cambridge, *n. d.*). Miyetti law library renders scanning services to its users for a fee.
- viii. **Digital library:** A digital library is a library in which collections are stored in digital formats and accessible by computers. The digital content may be stored locally, or accessed remotely via computer networks. A digital library is a type of information retrieval system (Witten and Bainbridge, 2009).
- ix. **Electronic resources and services:** Electronic resources and services have dominated the library of the 21st century. Libraries are now moving towards digital e-resources, which are found to be less expensive and more useful for easy access. This is especially helpful to distant learners who have limited time to access the physical libraries as digital could be accessed from outside through an internet connection. Resources such as CD-ROM, OPACs, E-Journals, E-Books, ETD, and Internet are speedily replacing the print media (Sharma, 2009). Miyetti law library has a complete form of electronic resources available for users.

Conclusion:

A legal library that wants to thrive in the 21st century must embrace the latest technologies to enable it to catch up with the demands of diverse legal information seekers. With Information Technology-based and traditional library resources and services joined together, a formidable hybrid system is set to the stage. Implementation of Information Technology in legal libraries facilitates access to the right information quicker and with minimal cost. Hybrid legal libraries utilize the emerging technologies to boost the image of the parent institution and also to lessen the work load of the library staff. Information Technologies in the legal library has broken the physical boundaries and enable the library to provide better services to the legal community.

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